

Improving Student's Writing Anecdotal Text Using Short Film as Media at SMKN Lhokseumawe

Sitti Aminah¹, Nuraiza², Iba Harliana³, Nurmalawati⁴

¹Bumi Persada University

²Jabal Ghafur University

³Malikussaleh University

⁴Bumi Persada University

Filed Road Medan - B. Aceh No.59 Alue Awe. Village, Medan-Banda Aceh Road, Bukit Indah

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
12 December 2022

Corresponding Author
Sitti Aminah

ABSTRACT

Writing learning in high school is foundation the next level in higher education later. In order to develop creativity in working in accordance with the demands of the Merdeka Learning Campus. In writing learning, it is hoped that students will not only be able to develop writing skills but also have to but also need to be careful to create narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts that are interesting to read. A text-based approach that is applied through a learning process that aims to motivate students. The formulation of the problem in this study is 1) how are students' learning outcomes in writing?, 2) how are the differences in learning outcomes using learning using short film media with conventional learning in writing. While the objectives of this study are 1) to determine student learning outcomes in learning, 2) to determine differences in student learning outcomes using conventional media and learning outcomes. This research uses quantitative methods in the form of experiments, namely testing a method in the learning process. The sample in this study was class X students at SMKN Lhokseumawe. Data was collected through initial observation, pretest, learning process, posttest and discussion of learning outcomes using short film media. While data processing using t-test and percentage. The results obtained in this study are 1) Student learning outcomes after using short film media reach an average KKM value of 70 based on the determination of the KKM curriculum values listed in KI-3 and KI-4, 2) T-test results at a significant level = 0.05 obtained t count . t table is 2.5 . 2.48. This shows that student learning outcomes using short film media in making anecdotal text essays have increased compared to students who are taught with conventional learning on the material of writing anecdotal text essays.

KEYWORDS: short film media, anecdotal tex

INTRODUCTION

Indonesian language lessons are required subjects in every school. Indonesian language learning serves to achieve one's language skills which include four aspects, namely speaking, listening, reading, and writing skills. However, in reality there are still many obstacles experienced by SMKN Lhokseumawe students in developing these four skills. One of them is writing skill. Writing is the most difficult activity compared to other aspects. Writing skills are not as easy as one might think, but special practice is required. [1] states that writing requires skill and accuracy in word choice in expressing ideas. Students' anecdotal writing skills are seen from the completeness and accuracy of writing anecdotal text structures and linguistic rules. [2] In the research title

"Anecdotal Text Writing Skills for Students of Class X.I Madrasah Aliyah Negeri Bintan", states an increase in students' Anecdotal text writing skills with the existence of an interesting media, which will invite students to think creatively. In this competency students are expected to be able to write anecdotal texts according to the steps of writing anecdotal texts (observing, finding topics, developing according to the structure of content and linguistic characteristics). Writing activities aim to express what is thought, felt and desired in written language, [1]

[3] A text-based approach that is applied through a learning process that aims to motivate students. Students can develop knowledge (KI-3) and skills (KI-4) in terms of understanding and compiling various types of texts according to what is

being taught. There are several basic competencies (KD) associated with the Anecdotal Texts in the Indonesian language lesson syllabus, namely 3.1 Understanding the structure and linguistic rules of anecdotal texts in accordance with linguistic structures and rules, 4.2 recreating anecdotal texts in accordance with linguistic structures and rules. These two KDs will be the focus of later research. The skill of writing anecdotal texts is one aspect of students' abilities that must be measured and assessed for their development in writing entertaining and funny texts with the aim of criticizing someone. Anecdotal text is used to convey criticism but not with harsh words that hurt. [4] states that Anecdotal texts have four types, namely; narrative type, dialogue type, poetry or song type, and picture type. The research will be the types of anecdotal text, narrative type, and image type. In this case, students are able to write a narrative essay in the type of anecdotal text after watching a short film that is shown.

Based on the results of the initial observations that the researchers conducted at SMKN Lhokseumawe, in general, students were less able to write anecdotal essays. This phenomenon is due to the absence of learning media that attracts students' interest in writing and which is able to arouse children's interest in writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotal text. The learning method used so far is only a form of lecture learning method. This lecture learning method is a form of learning process where the teacher is more active than the students. Students only listen to directions from the teacher without any props. Based on the results of these observations indicate that students' writing skills need to be improved again. It's proven that; (1) students have not been able to show the characteristics of Narrative Writing in the form of Anecdotal Text; (2) students have not been able to register topics that can be developed into writings characterized by Anecdotal Text; (3) students have not compiled a narrative essay in the form of anecdotal text about events that occur everyday that are funny; (4) students have not been able to compose Narrative essays in the form of Anecdotal Texts based on certain themes or topics, and (5) students have not been able to edit Narrative essays in the form of Anecdotal Texts written by friends in accordance with the indicators to be achieved in the Indonesian Language and Literature curriculum K- 13.

In connection with the above, the author tries to conduct a research using the method in the learning process of writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts. The method is a learning method using short film media. This method can arouse children's interest in writing after watching funny short films in the classroom. After the children watch the short film footage, the children are invited to think critically and express their ideas in written language. Relevant research has also been conducted [2] entitled "The Influence of the Use of Animated Film Media on Narrative Writing Skills for Class V Elementary School Students" stated that there was an

increase in learning to write. Based on this, the researcher will follow up the Indonesian language learning process on Writing Materials using Learning Media, namely Short Film Media

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Learning is an interaction process involving several components including: students, teachers, objectives, lesson content, methods, results and evaluations. [5] stated that writing skills are very complex because they require students to master the components in it, for example using correct spelling, choosing the right vocabulary, using effective sentences, and preparing good paragraphs. Writing skills are skills that must be applied in learning Indonesian in accordance with the objectives of education in Indonesia. The government seeks to improve the quality of education in Indonesia by changing the curriculum, namely the 2013 Curriculum (K-13). [6] said that in the 2013 Curriculum (K-13) Indonesian is not only functioned as a communication tool, but also as a means of thinking. Language is a means to express ideas and a complete idea is usually realized in the form of text.

[1] states, writing is a thought process that begins with the thought of the ideas to be conveyed, writing is a different form of communication from conversing; in the writing there is no intonation, facial expressions, physical movements, and those that do not accompany conversation; Writing is a form of communication that needs to be equipped with signs of explanation, rules, spelling, and punctuation. And writing is a form of communication to convey the author's ideas to an audience of readers who are limited by distance, place and time. Writing is giving birth and creating an expression of one's feelings and desires. [7] states that writing is one of the language skills used to communicate that writing is indirectly, not face to face with other people.

Writing skills are taught with the aim that students have the ability to express ideas, ideas, thoughts, experiences, and opinions correctly. Writing is essentially an effort to express what is seen, experienced, felt, and thought into written language [8] stating, writing skills will not be possessed by someone automatically, but must go through continuous practice and practice. With intensive practice can improve writing skills.

2.1 Understanding Anecdotal Text

An anecdote is a kind of story in the form of a narrative or often also called a narrative, derived from the English word narration which means story and narrative which means to tell something funny. [8] The goal of narrative writing is to provide the reader with a clear picture of the phases, steps, sequences, or sequences of events occurring. Narrative anecdotal text is a text in the form of a story in which it contains humor as well as criticism that is conveyed implicitly. [9] stated, interpreting anecdotes as short stories that are interesting because they are funny and memorable,

usually about important or famous people, and based on actual events. In line with that [10] states that an anecdote text is a text that contains someone's unusual experience, the unusual experience is conveyed to others with the aim of entertaining the reader. Thus, the notion of anecdote includes two basic elements, namely (1) actions or actions that occur in a series of time in the form of actions carried out by people or characters in a series of time and place, (2) anecdotes tell a life that is dynamic in a time series and full of humor. By using short film media, it is hoped that the PAKEM learning process (active, effective, and fun learning) will be more challenging and more meaningful.

Anecdotal text writing skills of students are seen from the completeness and accuracy of writing anecdotal text structures and linguistic rules. [10] states that there are five (5) anecdotal text structures, namely abstract (abstraction), orientation (orientation), problem (crisis), reaction (reaction), and coda (coda), the linguistic rules of the anecdotal text used are five (5), namely using lamp time, using rhetorical questions, using conjunctions or connecting words, using verbs, and using command sentences. First, the structure of anecdotal text, namely abstract (abstract) is the part at the beginning of the paragraph that serves to provide an overview of the content of the text, usually in the form of a sentence or the beginning of the background of a story. Orientation is the part that shows the beginning of the story or the background of how the event happened by telling the place, time, and participants who took part in the story. The emergence of a problem (crisis) is a part of a unique or unusual thing or problem that occurs to the author or the person being told. Reaction (reaction) is the part about how the author or the person being written resolves the problems that arise in the crisis section. Koda (coda) is the final part of the unique story. Usually contains a conclusion related to the entire content of the text.

2.2 Definition of Short Film

Short Film is an artistic and cultural copyrighted work which is an audio-visual communication medium based on cinematography, recorded on celluloid tape, video tape, or other technological inventions in all shapes and sizes through an electronic process. With or without sound, which can be displayed and displayed on other mechanical, electronic projection systems. A short film is a fictional film including an animated work that has a duration of no more than 60 minutes. There is also a short documentary film, which is a nonfiction film with the main content of documentation, information and knowledge which has a duration of no more than 60 minutes. The use of short film media as a learning medium in addition to attracting children's attention, which can stimulate or motivate children's activities. Short film media helps the recipient of the message to get a clearer and unforgettable response because between seeing and hearing can be combined into one. In connection with learning media which has become one of the important components in the

learning process, so that the learning media through "Short Films" is expected to be a teacher able to motivate students' enthusiasm for learning. That way the affective side of students will be more developed because students will play an active role in the learning. Benefits in the learning process is to facilitate interaction between teachers and students, with the aim of helping students learn optimally.

[11] that short films have a great ability to attract children's attention and interest. In addition, the appropriate use of short films can influence attitudes, behavior and can build character. [12], stated that short film media can increase learning motivation, bring fresh air to the learning atmosphere, and instill moral values. By using short film media, it is hoped that the PAKEM learning process (active, effective, and fun learning) will be more challenging and more meaningful. Based on the above, it is concluded that the short film media is a learning medium that can motivate students, bring a new atmosphere in learning and can instill moral values, so that the learning process is more active, creative, effective and fun and meaningful. However, keep in mind that not all short films are suitable as learning media, so the teacher must first select which ones are relevant and appropriate to be used as learning media.

METHOD

The reasearch is use quantitative methods by testing a method in the learning process. Begins with the problems of students in writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts. Then how writing learning process, and how to improve writing skill of narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts of students through short film media. The research location is at SMKN Lhokseumawe. The subjects of this study were 50 students of class X, divided into two classes. One class as an experimental class in testing the use of short film media during the writing learning process. One more class as a conventional class without media in the learning process. This was done to find out the comparison of the improvement in students' abilities in writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotes in the two classes. The instrument in this study used a written test, interviews, anecdotal text notes.

The data of this research is the result of anecdotal text writing skill test. The sample of this research was carried out randomly based on the process of sorting names randomly in the presence, which was then represented by one class which became the experimental class. Pretest, conducted to determine students' prior knowledge in understanding anecdotal texts. Then a post-test was carried out after the learning process took place using short film media in the experimental class. While the control class did not use short film media during the learning process to write texts.

The results of the anecdotal text writing ability test were then analyzed through steps, first identifying student test results based on the structure and linguistic rules used by students in anecdotal texts. Second, classify or classify the structures and

linguistic rules found in students' anecdotal texts. Third, interpret the structure and linguistic rules of the anecdotal texts found to process the data. Fourth, processing the data findings. The data processing technique used is quantitative data processing techniques used to process data in the form of numbers obtained from the skills of writing anecdotal texts in the form of scores. The results of the two classes will be a benchmark for comparison of the increase in students' abilities in writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts. Processing the data that has been obtained will be validated using SPSS statistical data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the post-test data on the ability to write anecdotal texts for class X SMKN Lhokseumawe various writing anecdotal texts in terms of the structure and linguistic rules of anecdotal texts. Assessment of student writing results using the Minimum Completeness

Criteria (KKM). The KKM value used at SMKN Lhokseumawe for Basic Competencies (KD) 4.6 Re-creating anecdotal texts by paying attention to the structure and linguistic rules of anecdotal texts, is 70. Students who get scores below 70 are categorized as moderately skilled and less skilled, students belonging to above 70 are categorized as skilled and highly skilled.

Table 1. Grades and Categories of Student Assessment Category Value

VALUE	CATEGORY
88 -100	Very Skilled
70 – 87	Skilled
50 – 69	Pretty Skilled
35 – 49	Less Skilled

As explained in the Theoretical Review, there are five anecdotal text structures, namely students' Anecdotal text writing skills seen from the completeness and accuracy of writing anecdotal text structures and linguistic rules. [10] states that there are five (5) anecdotal text structures, namely abstract (abstraction), orientation (orientation), problem (crisis), reaction (reaction), and coda (coda), the linguistic rules of the anecdotal text used are five (5), namely using the past tense, using rhetorical questions, using conjunctions or connecting words, using verbs, and using imperative sentences. First, the structure of anecdotal text, namely abstract (abstract) is the part at the beginning of the paragraph that serves to provide an overview of the content of the text, usually in the form of a sentence or the beginning of the background of a story. Orientation is the part that shows the beginning of the story or the background of how the event happened by telling the place, time, and participants who took part in the story. The emergence of a problem (crisis) is a part of a unique or unusual thing or problem that occurs to the author or the person being told. Reaction (reaction) is the part

about how the author or the person being written resolves the problems that arise in the crisis section. Koda (coda) is the final part of the unique story. Usually contains a conclusion related to the entire content of the text.

Implementation of teaching and learning activities carried out in accordance with the research schedule. In this case the researcher acts as a teacher. The teaching and learning process refers to the lesson plans that have been prepared. Observation (observation) is carried out simultaneously with the implementation of teaching and learning. So that it does not interfere with the teaching and learning process on the schedule listed in the class roster.

To find out the students' initial knowledge in writing anecdotal texts, a pretest was carried out. The pretest was conducted during the teaching and learning process of narrative writing skills in the form of anecdotes. The data on the results of the research pretest with the average value of narrative essay writing skills are below:

Table 2. The average value of writing skills text

Aspect	Average
Contents	21.2
Organization	15.1
Vocabulary	15.2
Language use	14.2
Mechanical	4.5
Average	70.2

Based on the results of the pretest in the table above, it shows that the level of students' ability in writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts in the category of obtaining an average score is sufficient. Based on the results of observations obtained in teaching and learning activities that; 1) lack of teacher motivation in conveying learning objectives. 2) the need for special skills for teachers so that students are motivated during learning. 3) the readiness of a teacher before the learning process begins is very important, so that the delivery of information related to learning can be fully absorbed by students.

Learning skills to write anecdotal texts requires an ability by a teacher, so that students are really skilled in writing these anecdotal texts. Anecdotal text is a text that tells a funny and exciting experience to the reader. So we need a media in the process of learning this writing skill.

In this study, researchers used a short film as a medium to improve students' ability to write narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts. At the end of the teaching and learning process using short film media, a post-test was conducted with the aim of knowing the level of success of students in writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts. The results obtained from the teaching and learning process using short film media can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Improving Essay Writing Ability Anecdote

Aspects	Pretest	Posttest	Improvement
Contents	21.2	23.5	2.3
Organization	15.1	17.5	2.4
Vocabulary	15.2	17.2	2
Language Usage	14.5	16.8	2.3
Mechanical	4.5	6.5	2
Average-	70.2	81.5	11.3

The main purpose of writing learning materials is that students have the skills to write anecdotal texts. In order for students' writing skills to develop as the learning process increases, media is needed. Learning media that improves students' abilities in writing narrative essay skills using short film media. Based on the results of the post-test conducted at the end of the lesson using short film media, there was an increase in the ability to write anecdotal texts. Based on the posttest results table above, it shows that; Student skill activities in writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts have increased and can be categorized as very skilled with an average score of 81.5.

The percentage increase in students' ability to write narrative essays in the form of anecdotes is based on the ability of 25 students. The improvement of students' abilities based on the respective aspects below; The list of scores from all students regarding the ability to write anecdotal texts is as follows: a. 15 people are classified in the category of very skilled scores, with a presentation value of 88 - 100, b. 6 people belong to the category of skilled scores with a percentage of 70 – 87, c. 4 people belonging to the category of moderately skilled scores with a presentation of 50 – 69, d. 0 people belong to the category of less skilled scores with a percentage of 35-49.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of the discussion above is that the increase in students' abilities in the ability to write narrative essays in the form of anecdotal texts occurs because of the learning process using learning media. The right media will support the skills of writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotes. Anecdotal text is a text that is told based on funny experiences that occur in everyday life. So it takes an incentive skill in the process of making a narrative essay in the form of an anecdote. Short film media is an appropriate medium in the

learning process of writing narrative essays in the form of anecdotal text.

But what must be considered is the role of a teacher who must understand the characteristics of each student. Teachers always give appreciation in the form of grades for student work, such as assignments, exams, and other work. This greatly affects the creativity of students everyday. For students themselves to achieve good learning, several things are needed, namely, responsibility like a student who wants to achieve goals, focus when the learning process takes place, be serious about completing all tasks assigned by the teacher. So that a learning process is achieved which is the main goal in achieving the KKM value of each student.

REFERENCES

1. Kurniawan, Heru. 2014. Communicative and Appreciative-Based Creative Writing Learning. Bandung: Rosdakarya.
2. Astuti, Widi, et al. 2014. The Effect of Using Animated Short Film Media on the Narrative Writing Skills of Grade V Students SD.Vol.2 No.2, 250-262-2014.
3. Curriculum 2013.2013. Outlines of the Indonesian Language Teaching Program. Jakarta: Depdikbud.
4. Slamet, I.I.W. Sarwo. 2015. Indonesian (compulsory) for Class X SMA/MA/SMK. Jakarta: Angkasa.
5. Kurniawan, Heru. 2014. Communicative and Appreciative-Based Creative Writing Learning. Bandung: Rosdakarya.
6. Priyatni, 2014. Learning Design in the 2013 Curriculum. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
7. Tarigan, H.G 2015. Writing as a Language Skill. London: Space.
8. Nurnaningsih, L.A. 2020. Improvement of Anecdotal Text Skills With MediaCaricature at SMAN I Baru Sopang. (SARASVATI Scientific Journal, Vol. 2, No. 2, December 2020 (p-ISSN 2685-6808, e-ISSN 2685-6005)
9. Justina. 2016. Productive Indonesian for SMA/SMK/MAK Class X. Jakarta: Erlangga.
10. Russman. 2012. Learning Models. Jakarta: Raja Grafindon Persada.
11. Sairo, Immanuel. 2018. Learning Strategies, Overview for Educators. West Kalimantan: STKIP Persada